

SCHOOL PERFORMANCE OF BOYS' PUBLIC PRIMARY SCHOOLS WITH MALE HEAD TEACHERS: EVIDENCE FROM PUBLIC SECTOR SCHOOLS IN DISTRICT GUJRAT

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Abstract

This research investigated the overall performance of boys' primary schools in the district of Gujrat, headed by male teachers, particularly in urban and rural schools. The research design was quantitative and descriptive, and a sample of 80 schools (40 urban and 40 rural) was selected using stratified random sampling. The information was gathered on a school performance observation checklist using a structured set of questions and analyzed using descriptive statistics (mean, standard deviation) and independent-samples t-tests to compare urban and rural schools. The findings showed that schools overall scored well in academic achievement, classroom practices, enrolment and retention, and school environment, with slightly lower performance in co-curricular activities. Urban schools consistently outperformed rural schools across all performance indices, and statistically significant differences were observed in academic achievement, classroom practices, enrolment and retention, co-curricular activities, school environment, and overall performance. The results indicate the significance of male head teachers' leadership in improving school performance and propose that specific interventions are required to increase resources, co-curricular activities, and the overall learning environment in rural schools.

Introduction:

Background of the Study

It is well known that school performance at the primary level is a key factor that determines the academic backgrounds of students, their social growth and success in education in the future. Primary education is the one that teaches the fundamental skills of literacy, numeracy, and socialization, which determine how the learner will develop in the next levels of education. In third world nations like Pakistan, most of the children especially those of underprivileged background attend public primary schools and

therefore their performance is a national issue in developing nations. The enhancement of the performance of schools at this level is strictly associated with the quality of education, equity, and socioeconomic development in the long run (Zancajo et al., 2021).

Among other school-related factors, it has always been established that Leadership is one of the most forceful determinants of school performance. Head teachers are significant when it comes to influencing the vision of schools, managing resources, overseeing school instruction

and providing a positive school climate. Effective school leadership helps in better teaching, teacher motivation and student performance. The studies show that having an effective and active head teacher in schools would be associated with a high level of organizational efficiency and higher academic results (Leithwood, Harris, and Hopkins, 2020).

The leadership aspect of the head teacher in boys of the public primary schools is further enhanced by the unique nature of the academic and behavioral traits of young boys. The schools of boys are characterized by the difficulties concerning the discipline, attendance, engagement, and retention that demand the firm and effective leadership and regular management practices. Boys head teachers with their conventional appointment in the public sector boys' schools are usually seen as role models and figures of authority capable of positively impacting the behavior and attitude of students towards learning. They can thus supervise the performance of the school directly through the approach on their leadership and how they relate to their staff and students (Hallinger, 2018).

School performance is a multidimensional concept that is not limited to the school performance in terms of academic performance. It also contains the indicators like the percentage of enrollment and retention, school attendance, classroom activities, co-curricular activities, school cleanliness, school discipline, and the general learning atmosphere. On the first level, these indicators are the sum total of the effectiveness of school management and leadership. The Head teachers have the responsibility of coordinating such dimensions by supervising instructions, providing support to the teacher, monitoring students and communicating with the parents and the community. The leadership role plays a very vital role especially in the public sector schools where resources are limited and efficient management and innovations are required (Hopkins, 2003).

The district of Gujrat located in Punjab province has a high population of boys' primary schools that are governed by the administrative body of the

School Education Department. Although there have been different government programs to ensure that there is betterment of primary education, the difference in school performance is still apparent across schools. Such differences could be explained by differences in leadership practice, teacher commitment, administrative efficiency and local contextual factors. Male head teachers who constitute a significant percentage of school leaders in boys primary schools are central in solving these problems and guaranteeing adequate degrees of school achievement (Shah and Sajjad, 2024).

In the existing literature on the topic of educational leadership, the effectiveness of head teachers is determined by their professional level, leadership approaches, ability to manage the administration, and the possibility to encourage the collaboration of teachers. Empirical research indicates that instructional leadership has a positive impact on teacher performance and learners. Nevertheless, most of the available studies have been based on secondary schools or mixed-gender schools but little is done concerning boys' public primary schools especially on the Pakistani context. This shortage of localized empirical research shows that the further study on the primary level is required (Lai and Cheung, 2015).

In addition to this, head teachers in the Pakistani public education system work under a difficult environment which is characterized by lack of autonomy, poor infrastructure, overclassroom, and administrative strains. Such limitations can impede their effectiveness in the leadership of schools and their performance. It is necessary to understand how the public primary schools of boys are functioning under male head teachers under these systemic constraints in order to establish the areas of strength and weakness in leadership. Professional development programs and policy reforms to enhance the school leadership can be informed by such understanding (Rizvi and Lingard, 2009).

It is especially pertinent, as the District Gujrat is somewhat representative of a wide educational environment, and a combination of urban, semi-

urban, and rural schools. Difference in socioeconomic status, parental involvement and access to learning materials could have a great impact in school performance. The analysis of boys' public primary schools whose heads are male in this district makes it possible to generate context-specific evidence that could be utilized in education planning and decision-making in districts and provinces (Chaudhry & Tajwar, 2020).

In addition, the focus on male head teachers is not to determine the level of leadership effectiveness in a gender manner but is known to be the existing administrative set up in the boys schools in the state sector. By examining school performance under male leadership, it gives a point of reference in the future comparative analysis with women head teachers or any combination of leadership. This kind of empirical evidence is needed in advocating inclusive and evidence-based policies on leadership in the educational system (Coleman, 2012).

To sum up, the issue of school performance in primary level has been a burning issue in the education system of Pakistan and head teachers have an influential role to play in determining the effectiveness of a school. Boys' primary schools, especially the public ones, need a strong leadership to overcome the academic, behavioral and administrative problems. Nevertheless, little empirical data exists on this specific topic, although the research on boys' schools, which are led by male head teachers, in the District Gujrat is significant. The current research will help close this gap by exploring important measurements of school performance in such schools, hence funding the existing body of research on educational leadership and offering practical recommendations to policymakers, administrators, and practitioners to enhance primary education in the state sector (Chandler, 2020).

Rationale of the Study

The performance of the public primary schools is one of the pointers of the effectiveness of an education system since it provides an indicator of

the quality of teaching, school management, and the level of student learning as the foundation level. The public primary schools of boys in Pakistan have a huge proportion of the school-going population in rural and semi-urban regions where there is a challenge in attaining quality education. Although the government is still trying to better the primary education, school performance differences are still being experienced, which means it is necessary to investigate the factors that still contribute to the differences in the performance of the schools. Of such factors, the leadership of schools, especially, school head teachers have become a very important determinant of school performance.

The responsibilities of the head teacher in the public primary schools are varied and include instructional supervision, administrative administration, maintenance of discipline and liaison with teachers, parents and education authorities. In male schools, the schools are always headed by male head teachers who are supposed to have a positive impact on the performance and the behaviors of the students. Nevertheless, very little empirical research is available with regard to the performance of boys' primary schools when under male head teachers with a special reference to localized settings like District Gujrat. Lack of such evidence renders policymakers and administrators to be unable to evaluate whether the leadership arrangements in place are effective. In addition, the available literature on school leadership in Pakistan has been restricted to secondary schools, and has analyzed the leadership styles in a generalized way without breaking down the information by type of school and gendered environments. Public primary schools of boys have administrative and instructional peculiarities that need special research. Knowledge of the performance of the schools in this particular setting is critical in the development of the leadership training programs, the improvement of the management practices in schools, and the increase of the school performance at the primary level.

The current research is thus reasonable since it aims at producing empirical data on the

performance of boys' primary schools that are headed by male teachers in District Gujrat. The research will seek to offer a profound insight into the effectiveness of these schools in their present operations as indicated by various outcomes of the performance of schools through different indicators. It is believed that the findings will enlighten educational planners, policymakers and school administrators on the areas and weaknesses of leadership and school management, thus helping to make evidence-based decisions and enhance primary education in the district and other areas.

Statement of the Problem

The basis of the whole education system lies in primary education and the performance of the public primary schools is very important in terms of providing students with the success in their academic life and the holistic development. Pakistan The public schools of boys form a large percentage of the public sector in the field of education and is an important part of the sector giving basic education to young children. In spite of the continued government efforts to enhance access, quality, and accountability in the primary education, there are still suspicions of the disparate school performance in various public primary schools. Such issues are frequently manifested in differences in the academic performance of students, the rates of their enrollments and retentions, discipline and the overall school atmosphere.

The leadership of schools, especially of the head teachers, is extensively considered as one of the major determinants of the school performance. The males are traditionally appointed as the head of boys public primary schools and charged with the responsibility of providing leadership in the running of instructional activities, teachers, ensuring discipline of the school and the proper running of schools. But in District Gujrat, there is no systematic and empirical evidence that clearly records the performance level of the boys public primary school under male head teacher. In the absence of such evidence, it is hard to conclude

that the existing leadership practices are successful in bringing the desired educational effects.

Besides, the current studies conducted in Pakistan have mostly considered leadership and secondary level or generally analyzed the performance of schools without giving due focus to the boys primary schools of the country as a separate entity. This knowledge gap in the literature constrains the capacity of policymakers and educational administrators to make sound decisions related to leadership development, resource distribution and policy changes at the primary level. This therefore necessitates the research to explore the performance of boys public primary schools headed by male principal teachers in a given local setting.

Thus, the issue that is covered by this study is the absence of empirical data on the performance of public primary schools that have male head teachers and boys in District Gujrat. The importance of this issue is the need to know the efficiency of school leadership at the primary level as well as to determine what should be improved to uplift the quality and efficiency of the public primary education.

Objective of the Study

1. To identify the degree of school performance of male headed boys primary schools in District Gujrat.
2. To compare the school performance of male head teachers of urban and rural boys public primary schools in District Gujrat.

Research Question

1. What is the school performance of male head teachers in public primary schools in District Gujrat?
2. Do urban and rural boys' public primary schools with male head teachers in District Gujrat perform significantly differently?

Review of Literature

The performance of schools in the primary level is determined by a mixture of factors such as teacher

quality, students, school resources, and leadership. School leadership has always been ranked as one of the greatest predictors of school success. Good head teachers are very important in developing the vision, culture and efficiency of the running of a school which directly influences teacher performance and student acquired learning. Primary school leadership is of special concern as the initial abilities developed by students at this stage have long-term consequences in terms of their academic career (Leithwood, Harris, and Hopkins, 2020; Bush, 2019).

School leadership has changed over the years to go beyond the administrative management to encompass instructional leadership, transformational leadership and distributed leadership. Instructional leadership focuses on enhancement of teaching and learning techniques, tracking student accomplishment and offering teacher-professional growth. Transformational leadership is about staff motivation, staff inspiration, and collaboration as well as the encouragement of innovation in schools. Distributed leadership acknowledges the common obligations of teachers and staff in the decision-making processes which has the ability to promote organizational effectiveness. All these leadership models emphasize the leading role of the head teacher in determining the performance of schools (Heck and Hallinger, 2014).

A number of studies have established that there exists a positive correlation between an effective leadership at schools and student outcomes. Head teachers who give clear direction, high expectations and those who monitor teaching practices regularly are likely to enhance teacher performance and the student achievement as well. Leadership styles that have been found to result in improved classroom instruction and increased student engagement include their promotion of teacher collaboration, teacher mentoring, and offering constructive feedback. Concerning the primary schools, the administration that is engaged in an instruction process and visible in classrooms fosters the culture of accountability and academic standards (Day and Sammons et al., 2016).

School performance is a multidimensional construct, which is more than the academic performance of students. Though the test scores and grades are a significant indicator, the other factors like student enrolment, retention rate, classroom control, co-curricular activities and school environment are also crucial. Head teachers make a difference through proper planning, proper management of resources and promotion of positive school climate. As an illustration, in schools that have proactive leaders, there are less dropouts, increased attendance, and organized co-curricular activities, leading to the comprehensive development of the student (Pont, 2020).

The head teachers in the boy public primary schools have a special role to play owing to the behavioral and developmental aspect of male students. Research has postulated that boys tend to need more manipulative discipline measures, effective role models and attention to keep them focused and motivated in their studies. In boys schools male head teachers appear as an authority figure who can serve as a good example of behavior and can make high achievement standards based on academic and social performance. In such environments, leadership that can help to meet the instructional and behavioral needs of students is important to enhance the overall school performance (Kovačević & Hallinger, 2019).

The studies conducted under the framework of the main secondary schools have identified various predicaments of the head teachers. The capability of the head teachers to practice leadership can be limited by lack of autonomy, insufficient resources, overcrowded classes and the administrative overheads. Such limitations are especially common in state-funded schools, where the financial constraints and policy regulations might impede the access to teaching resources, professional growth programs, and assistant staff. Nevertheless, the main flaw of the system is that the head teachers with high leadership qualities and responsive to the contextual limitations have been found to improve the school's performance considerably (Noor and Nawab, 2022).

Localized studies have been stressed upon in studies undertaken in South Asian settings, as far as the research is concerned in the context of comprehending the role of school leadership and performance. The effectiveness of the head teachers may depend on contextual factors like the socioeconomic conditions, parent involvement, teacher qualification, and the community support. With mixed urban and rural areas, schools in those districts can have vast differences in performance, which presupposes the necessity to lead in a manner that is specific to the context. The empirical evidence that can be given through the investigations of the performance of the boys primary schools under the head of a male can be used in the context of targeted interventions and policy reforms (Shah, 2017).

Differences in school performance in terms of the characteristics of leadership have also been studied comparatively. Results indicate that leadership behaviors comprising of instructional leadership and transformational and distributed leadership approaches have been demonstrated by head teachers to be more effective in enhancing teacher and student outcomes. Also, professional qualifications and years of experience of the head teachers have been linked to the increased levels of school effectiveness. It is also observed that schools that have head teachers that have high levels of training in educational leadership have a better planning, monitoring, and engagement with students, which ultimately lead to better performance in schools (Leithwood, 2021).

Although the literature has been substantial on the topic of school leadership and performance in secondary and mixed-gender schools, there has been little research on boys schools in the public primary schools. This gap constrains the knowledge of the transformation of leadership practices to the performance results that can be measured in these schools. The exploration of this association in the local setting of the District Gujrat is also necessary to have actionable knowledge that would help develop leadership programs, provide resources and plan policies. The findings of such studies may be used to determine the most effective leadership strategies

that can be applied to improve the performance of schools under similar conditions (Malik et al., 2022).

To summarize, the literature has pointed out at all times the central role of the head teacher in shaping the performance of a school in various aspects. Good leadership does not just lead to an increase in academic performance but also good management of schools, participation of students as well as learning environment. The role of male head teachers in the public primary schools in boys is especially important since they are looked upon as role models and disciplinarians and they influence the academic growth and behavioral growth. Although there is literature on the leadership in schools, there is a gap that requires contextual research that looks at the performance of the boys primary school in areas where male leaders are in charge, especially in areas such as Gujrat. Such studies will address the gaps in current knowledge and offer some practical recommendations on how to reinforce leadership practices and enhance the performance of primary schools in the public (Kiplimo, 2023).

Research Methodology

The present research follows a quantitative research design with descriptive research design to investigate the extent of school performance in male headed primary schools in District Gujrat. The descriptive design is applicable in this research because the researcher will be able to determine the current state of school performance, determine trends, and offer empirical data without any manipulation of variables.

The study population entails all the boys' public primary schools in the District Gujrat. These are schools that are run by the School Education Department and the majority of them are headed by male head teachers. The population represents both the urban and the rural schools, which will make the study to represent the varied educational environments in the district.

The study sample was 80 publicly controlled primary schools of boys with male heads. This was done using stratified random sampling to provide

proportional representation of both the urban and rural schools. The sampling method increases the generalizability of the results and ensures fairness in sampling in various school contexts.

Instrumentation

In order to gather data on the performance of boys led at the time of boys' primary school, where male teachers are at the helm the two instruments used in the study were a school performance observation checklist and structured questionnaire. The observation checklist was set in such a way that it will offer an objective evaluation of school performance on a variety of fronts, among them being academic performance, enrollment and retention, classroom practices, co-curricular activities, and cleanliness and learning environment of the school. All aspects were measured with the help of a Likert-type scale, which allowed quantifying and statistically analyzing the level of performance. The structured questionnaire was given to the head teachers and the selected teachers to elicit the perception of these teachers on the aspect of school leadership, instructional activities, teacher motivation, classroom management, and the general school climate. Checks were taken based on a five-point Likert scale that runs back to strongly disagree to strongly agree. The combination of these two instruments, helped the study to obtain both objective and subjective information using direct observation and school staff respectively, to have a complete picture of school performance with male head teachers.

Data Collection

After getting the permission of the School Education Department the data were collected in the public primary schools of the selected boys in District Gujrat. The researcher paid visits to every school and noted academic performance, classroom activities, student enrollment and retention, co-curricular activities and general school atmosphere using a checklist. Moreover, a structured questionnaire was provided to head teachers and selected teachers to provide their leadership perceptions, classroom management, and school climate. Participants were given a choice and the study was conducted with a sense of confidentiality which offered objective and subjective data.

Data Analysis

The data obtained were evaluated through descriptive statistics to identify the performance at school among boys in public primary schools headed by male teachers. Each performance indicator, i.e. academic achievement, classroom practices, enrollment and retention, co-curricular activities, and school environment were calculated in terms of mean scores, standard deviations and percentages. Moreover, the school effectiveness between urban and rural schools was compared as well in order to determine school effectiveness differences between various settings. The findings were tabulated in order to have a clear view of the trends, patterns and differences in school performance between urban and rural areas.

Table 1: School Performance of Boys' Public Primary Schools (N=80)

Performance Indicator	Mean	Standard Deviation
Academic Achievement	4.01	0.40
Classroom Practices	3.98	0.35
Enrollment & Retention	4.10	0.31
Co-curricular Activities	3.83	0.43
School Environment & Cleanliness	3.98	0.36
Overall Performance	3.98	0.37

Table 1 shows the general performance of 80 primary schools (public) in District Gujrat that are attended by boys. The results reveal that the

schools perform well in most indicators. Enrollment and Retention (M = 4.10, SD = 0.31) gave the highest mean score, meaning that the

highest number of students is on regular enrollment and retention at these schools. The rating of Academic Achievement ($M = 4.01$, $SD = 0.40$) and Classroom Practices ($M = 3.98$, $SD = 0.35$) were also rated as high, thus showing that there was effective teaching and learning activities. School Environment and Cleanliness also scored on the same ($M = 3.98$, $SD = 0.36$) to show that there was a clean and favorable learning

environment. Mean of Co-curricular Activities ($M = 3.83$, $SD = 0.43$) indicated that although they are available, more can still be done to develop the activities. In general, the overall performance of schools was high ($M = 3.98$, $SD = 0.37$), which means that the schools of boys in the District Gujrat are functioning well with male head teachers, especially in the main academic and functional fields.

Table 2: School Performance of Urban Boys' Public Primary Schools (N=40)

Performance Indicator	Mean	Standard Deviation
Academic Achievement	4.12	0.35
Classroom Practices	4.05	0.30
Enrollment & Retention	4.20	0.28
Co-curricular Activities	3.95	0.40
School Environment & Cleanliness	4.10	0.32
Overall Performance	4.08	0.33

The results of Table 2 indicate the general performance of the public primary schools of urban boys in the District Gujrat (N=40). The data shows that the urban schools were high in all indicators. Enrollment and Retention ($M = 4.20$, $SD = 0.28$) had the highest mean score which indicates that there is high student retention and regular attendance. The scores of Academic Achievement ($M = 4.12$, $SD = 0.35$), Classroom Practices ($M = 4.05$, $SD = 0.30$), and School Environment and Cleanliness ($M = 4.10$, $SD = 0.32$) were also high, which testified to the

effective teaching, well-managed classrooms, and supporting learning environment. Co-curricular Activities had a little less mean ($M = 3.95$, $SD = 0.40$) which means that improvement can be made in offering organized extracurricular programs. Comprehensively, the overall performance of the urban schools was high ($M = 4.08$, $SD = 0.33$), and this indicates that the current performance of the urban boys' primary schools in District Gujrat is working well with male head teachers, especially in academic and operation aspects.

Table 3: School Performance of Rural Boys' Public Primary Schools (N=40)

Performance Indicator	Mean	Standard Deviation
Academic Achievement	3.89	0.42
Classroom Practices	3.90	0.38
Enrollment & Retention	4.00	0.33
Co-curricular Activities	3.70	0.45
School Environment & Cleanliness	3.85	0.38
Overall Performance	3.87	0.39

Table 3 gives the general performance of the rural boys in the government primary schools (N=40) in the District Gujrat. The results show that among the majority of the indicators, rural schools were relatively high in performance. Enrollment and Retention ($M = 4.00$, $SD = 0.33$) had the highest

mean score, which indicates that student attendance and retention are not very bad. Classroom Practices ($M = 3.90$, $SD = 0.38$) and Academic Achievement ($M = 3.89$, $SD = 0.42$) were of moderate level, as well, and indicative of a satisfactory level of teaching and learning

outcomes. School Environment and Cleanliness ($M = 3.85$, $SD = 0.38$) was rated as high, which implies that the school environment is relatively kept in excellent conditions, and Co-curricular Activities ($M = 3.70$, $SD = 0.45$) scored the lowest, implying a limited participation in extra-curricular

activities. The overall performance of the rural schools was average ($M = 3.87$, $SD = 0.39$), showing that the rural boys public primary schools are performing satisfactorily with the male head teachers although slightly lower in most of the areas than its counterparts in urban schools.

Table 4: Comparison of School Performance Between Urban and Rural Boys' Public Primary Schools

Performance Indicator	Urban Schools N=40		Rural Schools N=40		t-value	p-value
	Mean	SD	Mean	SD		
Academic Achievement	4.12	0.35	3.89	0.42	2.58	0.012
Classroom Practices	4.05	0.30	3.90	0.38	2.01	0.049
Enrollment & Retention	4.20	0.28	4.00	0.33	2.73	0.008
Co-curricular Activities	3.95	0.40	3.70	0.45	2.29	0.025
School Environment & Cleanliness	4.10	0.32	3.85	0.38	2.71	0.009
Overall Performance	4.08	0.33	3.87	0.39	3.06	0.003

Table 4 gives a comparative school performance between urban and rural boys primary schools of the District Gujrat. The outcomes show that urban schools were always performing better as compared to rural schools in all the performance indicators. Academic Achievement was greater in urban schools ($M = 4.12$, $SD = 0.35$) than compared to rural schools ($M = 3.89$, $SD = 0.42$) with a significant difference ($t = 2.58$, $p = 0.012$). On the same note, Classroom Practices performed better in cities ($M = 4.05$) than in rural schools ($M = 3.90$), which was also statistically significant ($t = 2.01$, $p = 0.049$). The same was also true in Enrollment & Retention, Co-curricular Activities as well as School Environment and Cleanliness with urban schools scoring much higher than rural schools. The $t = 3.06$, $p = 0.003$ indicates that the overall performance of urban schools ($M = 4.08$, $SD = 0.33$) was significantly higher as compared to that of rural schools ($M = 3.87$, $SD = 0.39$).

Conclusions

This research shows that the overall performance of boys' primary schools in District Gujrat, whose heads are men, is quite high. Academic achievement, classroom practices, enrolment and retention, and school environment were scored consistently high and co-curricular activities despite their presence performed slightly below

the range. Comparison of the school location revealed that urban schools had higher results in all the performance indicators, with significant differences existing in the academic achievement, classroom practices, enrolment and retention, co-curricular activities, school environment, and overall performance. These findings are indicative that leadership efficacy, access to resources, and school atmosphere in urban schools are some of the factors that could lead to better school performance whereas rural schools, though performing adequately, can need more support in the areas of instruction quality, student achievement, and extra-curricular activities. In general, the study identifies the paramount importance of male head teachers to the high school performance and indicates the necessity of the special interventions to eliminate the performance disparities between urban and rural schools.

Discussion

The current study considered the general performance of boys' primary schools in District Gujrat under male-led head teachers, giving much emphasis on rural and urban schools. The results point to the fact that the schools were relatively well performing in terms of most of the indicators such as academic achievement, classroom

practices, enrolment and retention, and school environment. The performance was slightly lower in co-curricular activities implying that the activities are provided though they might need additional development to be the same as the academic performance as well as operations. These findings will complement the previous studies that have highlighted the fact that effective school leadership has a positive impact on the academic and organizational performance in the primary school setting (Leithwood, Harris, and Hopkins, 2020; Heck and Hallinger, 2014).

It was also discovered in the study that the urban schools performed better than the rural schools in all the performance criteria and the difference were statistically significant. Urban schools were found to have greater academic performance, superior classroom activities, superior enrolment and retention, superior co-curricular activities and superior maintained school climate. The result is consistent with the studies conducted in the past which note that providing school materials, facilities and access to trained personnel in urban environments are important contributors to high school achievement (Bush and Glover, 2016). Although rural schools were fairly performing well, they also had a range of challenges, including insufficient instructional resources, lack of teachers, and underdeveloped infrastructure, which could hamper their performance (Khan et al., 2019).

The findings also emphasize the critical importance of male head teachers in determining the performance of boys in its public primary education. Instructional leadership, classroom observation, teacher motivation, and conducive school environment were some of the leadership practices that were evident in the high overall performance that had been seen in both urban and rural schools. This confirms previous results according to which successful leadership in schools is closely related to student achievements and organizational success of primary school (Hallinger, 2018).

Also, the study points out to a disparity in co-curricular achievement, particularly in the rural schools and this finding is in tandem with the

research that extracurricular activities are not well developed in schools that lack resources (Hopkins, 2003). Intensifying co-curricular programs may lead to the overall development of pupils and enhance interaction, enthusiasm, and school atmosphere (Day and Sammons, 2016).

Recommendations

According to the results of this study, to alleviate this performance gap between the rural boys and the urban schools, it will be advised that the policymakers and the education administrators should give special attention to the rural boys' public primary schools. This involves the enhancement of infrastructure, delivery of instructional and learning materials and the availability of qualified teachers. Professional development programs on instructional leadership programs, classroom management as well as co-curricular program enhancement should be offered to school leaders especially, male head teachers. Co-curricular activities in both the urban and the rural schools should also be enhanced to have the students developed in a thorough manner. Moreover, monitoring and evaluation systems should be incorporated regularly to measure school performance and intervention to promote equity and quality of all the public primary schools within the District of Gujrat.

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